

International Journal of Advances in Materials Science and Engineering (IJAMSE)

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Scope & Topics

International Journal of Advances in Materials Science and Engineering (IJAMSE) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the Materials Science and Engineering. The journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on theoretical and practical aspects of Materials Science and Engineering.

The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on Materials Science and Engineering advancements, and establishing new collaborations in these areas. Original research papers, state-of-the-art reviews are invited for publication in all areas of Materials Science and Engineering.

Topics of interest include but are not limited to, the following

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to

- Art Conservation Science
- Biomaterials, tissue engineering
- Ceramics
- Composites
- Corrosion
- Diffraction studies
- Energy
- Fracture of materials
- Magnetic Materials
- Materials for Electronics and Photonics
- Materials Synthesis & Processing
- Materials Theory, Computation, and Design
- Mechanical properties
- Metals and alloys
- Nanomaterials, Nano particulates and nanocomposites
- Polymers
- Self-Assembly
- Solar energy
- Surfaces and Interfaces

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through the [Submission System](#) or ijamsejournal@wireilla.com. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline** : **August 23, 2020**
- Acceptance Notification : September 23, 2020
- Final Manuscript Due : September 01, 2020
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us

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